

THE ROLE OF CLIPPINGS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. Clipping is the word-formation process which consists in the reduction of a word to one of its parts in, other words, it is a derivational way of making new words by reduction. This article describe about the role of clipping in English language.

Keywords: abbreviation, clipping, initial clipping, final clipping, medial clipping, complex clipping.

There are so many ways to derive new words in English language and all together help enrich the language vocabulary. According to Koonin, one of the ways of making new words is clipping. It is not merely by borrowing from abroad, or by semantic changes in already existing words, but also by making of new words that English language has augmented its resources. (3. 137) Clipping helps quietly well to English language for making new words. From a sociolinguistic perspective, the usage of clippings is often restricted to a particular social group within society. In youth language, but also in expert language, the use of clippings displays a speaker's familiarity with the subject matter as well as it expresses and strengthens the speaker's belonging into a certain social group.

In linguistics, clipping is the word-formation process which consists in the reduction of a word to one of its parts in, other words, it is a derivational way of making new words by reduction. These shortened words are used in sentences like the whole word. Raevsika defines that clipping is a special category of word-making presented by the process of shortening which consists in the reduction of a word to one of its parts. Shortening is a development which has linguistic value of its own in various languages and must not be left unmentioned here as relevant to word-formation in English. Clipping is not so much a method of forming new words as of altering old ones without changing their meaning. (4.102)

According to Marchand, clippings are not coined as words belonging to the standard vocabulary of a language. They originate as terms of a special group like schools, army, police, the medical profession, etc. While clipping terms of some influential groups can pass into common usage, becoming part of Standard English, Clipping is different from back-formation – back-formation may change the part of speech or the word's meaning, whereas clipping creates shortened words from longer words, but does *not* change the part of speech or the meaning of the word. (6. 45) Clipping consists in the cutting of one or several syllables of a word. In many cases the stressed syllable is preserved. Ex. *Alf* from *Alfred*. (1. 203)

Clipping is classified into the following types depending on which part of the word is clipped:

- Words that have been shortened at the end: *ad* (*advertisement*), *lab* (*laboratory*), *Jap* (*Japanese*), *doc* (*doctor*), *sis* (*sister*), *vac* (*vacuum-cleaner*);
- Words that have been shortened at the beginning: *car* (*motor-car*), *phone* (*telephone*), *cast* (*broadcast*);
- Words in which syllables have been omitted from the middle so called syncope: *maths* (*mathematics*), *specs* (*spectacles*);
- Words that have been shortened at the beginning and at the end: *flu* (*influenza*), *tec* (*detective*), *frig* (*refrigerator*). (2. 61)

Shortened verbs like *rev* from *revolve* and *tab* from *tabulate* are very rare. Clipped adjectives are also few in numbers. Here belong: *comfy* (comfortable), *awk* (ward), *imposs(ible)*, *mizzy* (miserable). (4.103) The shortening of words means substituting a part for a whole, part of the word is taken away and used for the whole. **For example.** *demo* (demonstration), *dub* (double), *doc* (doctor), *fig* (figure), *Mrs* (missis). (5.49)

According to Irina Arnold, clipping mainly consists of the following types:

1. Initial clipping
2. Final clipping
3. Medial clipping

4. Complex clipping (7.)

Initial clipping is shortening word by leaving out the initial part of a word and retaining the final part of it. For instance, *plane* (airplane), *phone* (telephone), *site* (website), *net* (Internet), etc.

Final clipping, the most common type, is shortening of the word by retaining the initial part. For instance: *ad* (advertisement), *cable* (cablegram), *gas* (gasoline), *fax* (facsimile), *memo* (memorandum) etc.

Medial clipping is the shortening with the middle part of the word which left out equally few. For example, *fancy* (fantasy), *ma'am* (madam), *maths* (mathematics), *fridge* (refrigerator), *flu* (influenza) etc.

Complex clipping is the shortening of the word that one part of the original compound most often remains intact. For example, *cablegram* (*cable telegram*), *op art* (*optical art*), *org-man* (*organization man*), *sci fi* (*science fiction*), *rom com* (*romantic comedy*) etc. Sometimes both halves of a compound are clipped as in *navicert* (*navigation certificate*).

From these explanations we can see that clipping can be formed any place of the word and we should know its whole structure and its meaning. If we do not know its whole form then we cannot realize the meaning of the clipped word.

Clippings do not always coincide in meaning with the original word. Ex. *doc* and *doctor* have the meaning one who practices medicine, but *doctor* is also the highest degree given by a university to a scholar or scientist and a person who received such a degree whereas *doc* is not used with these meanings. However, in everyday conversation, clipping can also be used to people's name. We can say *Cat* for *Catherine*, *Mike* for *Michael*, *Pat* for *Patricia*, *Leo* for *Leonardo* etc. It proves that clipping is not just for words, but also for names.

In conclusion, we can see lots of clippings in sentences and the meaning remains the same. In other words, they are in the same part of speech according to their whole words. Clipping is not used in scientific writing and formal conversation.

But we can use it in informal ways. Especially, while people are speaking, they also use it. So, clipping is a good way in spoken.

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